

Linguistenspiel

1 Setting

You are an aspiring young linguist who tries to navigate the world of linguistic Academia. You explore new phenomena in new languages, you try to find a job, and you try to not forget the fun things in life beyond linguistics. There are several ways to win: build a coherent theory, do research in all macroareas, become emeritus or, if anything else fails, be the one who had most fun.

2 Content

The deck contains the following cards:

24 language cards	12 mentor cards	6 software cards	7 employee cards
60 research cards	21 event cards	8 institution cards	6 fun cards
12 book cards	7 device cards	9 publication cards	3 significant other cards

You will need one six-sided die and a way to keep track of ● and ♥ (eg tokens).

3 Setup

Every player gets the a starting card `Affirmative clauses` and one language card. This is what they did their master's thesis on, for instance Rapa Nui (The language of the Easter Islands). Place the language card above the card `Affirmative clauses`. Every player gets one 🟡, representing money and one ♡, representing motivation.

Discard any remaining `Affirmative clauses` from the deck. Then, deal every player 4 cards.

4 Languages

The players do research on languages, like Rapa Nui or English. They start with one language, and can only play cards in the column of that language at first. They can explore other languages, at a cost, and put the corresponding language card next to the existing languages.

Each language is part of one of **six macroareas**: AFRICA, EURASIA, AUSTRALIA, PAPUNESIA, NORTH AMERICA, SOUTH AMERICA.

5 Research

Once you have explored a language, you can do research on it. In order to do research, place a research card somewhere below the language card. All research cards together form your theory. For instance, suppose your initial language is Rapa Nui, and you start with `Affirmative clauses`. In a later turn, you add `Agreement` below. You then play English to the right and add `Nominalization` in a following turn. Your theory now consists of three components, `Affirmative clauses` and `Agreement` in Rapa Nui and `Nominalization` in English. At later points in time, you can complement it with other research cards, like `Number` or `Politeness`. Your theory will continue to grow in depth (for each language) and breadth (across languages).

5.1 Connectors

Research cards have connectors, which link the theory. Each research card in your graph must satisfy the following criteria

1. it belongs to one language
2. it is connected to the other cards via at least one connector
3. each of its connectors point to another connector, or to the void

Each research cards belongs to one linguistic domain: PHONOLOGY, MORPHOLOGY, SYNTAX, SEMANTICS, PRAGMATICS.

5.2 Requirements

Some phenomena are easy to research, and your MA qualifies them to approach them. These cards have a requirement of 0. Other phenomena are more difficult and you have to have some prior acquaintance to be able to do research on them. In the sample game, you have already researched `Agreement`, which gives you +1 on

your knowledge of SYNTAX, and Nominalization, which gives you +1 on MORPHOLOGY. There are other ways to increase your competence in domains as well, like **books**, **mentors**, or **computer programs**. Expertise in the macroarea a language is spoken in lowers the requirements as well.

If you want to play the card Raising, you will have to fulfill the requirement of SYNTAX □. You already have 1 knowledge of syntax via Agreement, so you are fine. If you wanted to play Heavy NP-shift, which has a requirement of SYNTAX □□, you would have to wait for your knowledge of syntax to increase before you can play it.

6 Victory conditions

As you build your theory, you can choose one of two main paths to victory: the formalist path or the typologist path. To win a **formalist victory**, you have to construct a coherent victory without any loose ends. Each connector on every card must point to another connector. No connector may point to the void.

To win a **typologist victory**, you have to have a theory which encompasses languages from all macroareas. NB: languages without any research conducted do not count. At least one research card must be present for a language to tick off that particular macroarea.

You can also win an **emeritus victory**. To win this, you have to supervise either two postdocs or one postdoc and two PhDs until their term ends. Be warned: this is a thorny path! You will need a publication, be hired at two institutions and then recruit your employees. See below how to accomplish the different steps.

Finally, if there are no more cards that can be played, there is **no academic victory**. In that case, the player with the most ♡ at the end wins. See below on how to acquire ♡.

7 Career

You start without a job, and hence without revenue. While you are **without a job**, you have one action. You cannot hire employees. The first job you can get will be **associate professor**. You get 1 ● at the beginning of your turn. You can now **hire PhDs**, and you still have one action. From the second job onwards, you will be **full professor**. You still get 1 ● a turn. You can **hire PhDs and postdocs**. Your employees can perform actions as normal, but you do not have any time to do research until you retire. Instead, you can become **reviewer 2** and move one card from the “Left For Further Research” to the graveyard pile (see §8.2.16).

8 Turns

Each turn consists of the action phase and the redraw phase. In the action phase, you perform one action (more if you have employees). In the redraw phase, you fill up your hand until your current hand limit.

8.1 Graveyard pile and “Left For Further Research” pile

There are two discard piles. Cards which are played and which have had effects, like event cards, go to the **graveyard pile**. They are no longer accessible in the game. Cards which are discarded because the player did not have time to deal with them go to the **“Left For Further Research” pile**. They can be retrieved at later points during the game.

8.2 Action phase

In the action phase, you can perform one action (more if you have employees). You can do one of the following:

1. play one card from your hand;
2. pay 1 ● and play the top card from the “Left For Further Research” pile;
3. work at McDonald’s. Discard one of your cards and put it on the “Left For Further Research” pile. Take 1 ●. The card you discard has no other effects.
4. spend time with your significant other;
5. apply for a job which is available on the table;
6. work on your publication.

Cards come in different categories, discussed below.

8.2.1 Flip patties

Sometimes you simply need money and cannot find the time to do research. Discard one of the cards on your hand to the “Left For Further Research” pile and take 1 ●. In the beginning of a game, this is a very frequent action.

8.2.2 Play research card

In order to play a research card, announce the language where you want to do research, ie where you want to put the card. Check that you meet the **scientific requirements** (like PHONOLOGY □□□ for instance) and that the intended position is legal with regard to connectors. If the research is done in a language in a macroarea you have some bonuses (via books or mentors), these bonuses lower the requirements correspondingly. You can buy missing requirement points at the rate of 5 ●/point. If you have only PHONOLOGY +2, but you need PHONOLOGY □□□, you can thus pay 5 ● to make up for the difference.

8.2.3 Play language card

- Announce which language you want to play.
- Make sure that you meet the **scientific requirements** for that language (eg PHONOLOGY □□□, see above at “play research card”). If the language is from a macroarea you have some bonuses in (via books or mentors), these bonuses reduce the requirement accordingly. You can buy missing requirement points at the rate of 5 ●/point. If you have only PHONOLOGY +2, but you need PHONOLOGY □□□, you can thus pay 5 ● to make up for the difference.
- Choose whether you want to put it to the left or to the right of the other languages you have done research on. Note that you cannot put the new language next to an existing language you have not done any research on.
- Pay the **exploration cost**. The exploration cost is equal to the number of languages already present in front of you. If you have already four language cards in front of you, playing the fifth will cost you 4 ●. The price is reduced by your knowledge in TYPOLOGY. If you have +2 in TYPOLOGY, you would only have to pay 2 ● instead of 4.

8.2.4 Play mentor card

Mentors are senior researchers who help and support you. Typically, there are no requirements for playing a mentor card, but some are nasty and make you lose one ♥.

8.2.5 Play book card

Books permanently increase your knowledge of a scientific domain or of a macro area. Put the card in front of you. Each book costs 1 ●.

8.2.6 Play device card

You can buy microphones, cameras, and computers. These give various bonuses. Computers furthermore allow you to install programs. Pay one ● and put the card in front of you.

8.2.7 Play software card

If you have a computer, you can install software on it. All software is open source, so you do not have to pay for it.

8.2.8 Play fun card

Play the card and put it on the graveyard pile. Take one ♡.

8.2.9 Play event card

Play the card and put it on the graveyard pile. Some cards will make you lose one ♡. If you have no ♡, you cannot play the card.

8.2.10 Play publication card

Play the publication card and put it in front of you. In order to arrive at a successful publication, you have to meet the requirements on the card. Typically, you have to write 2 or 3 sections, which have requirements (like PHONOLOGY 5 or AFRICA 4). You can try to fulfill one requirement in the turn you bring the card into play.

Publication requirements

1. Working on your publication requires inspiration. Pay 1 ♡.
2. In order to **fulfill the requirement**, roll the dice and exceed the threshold given for that requirement, applying your bonuses. If the first requirement is SYNTAX 5 and you have a current syntax SCORE of +2, you must roll 3 or higher. For **macroarea requirements**, each research card below a language from that macroarea counts gives you a bonus of +1.
3. Rolling the dice takes one action, but is included in the action which brings the publication card into play.
4. If you succeed for one requirement, put a token on the card to signal this. If you fail, you can still try again on any subsequent turn.

For a publication with three requirements, you would typically spend at least three turns.

8.2.11 Continue publication

Choose one of your publications. Pay one ♡ and roll the dice for the topmost requirement which is not yet met as explained above. You will typically not play a card this turn, and hence you do not have to fill up your hand either. Once all requirements are met, your article is published. Having a publication is necessary to apply for a job.

8.2.12 Play institution card

Play an institution card. A position is being announced as vacant. You are the first to apply, but you must have a publication in order to do so. You have to roll the dice for each of the listed required competences (like SYNTAX 6) separately, adding any bonuses from your research cards, mentors, books, devices etc. If you are successful in all rolls, you got the job. Otherwise, the card remains on the table, and other players can apply. If you already had a job before, you are now full prof. Your former position becomes vacant and is available for other players to apply for.

8.2.13 Apply for vacant position

You can apply for a vacant position which is available on the table. Roll the dice as described above. You typically will not play a card in this turn, and hence you will not redraw cards. If you are successful, you are hired, and your current position (if any) becomes vacant. Otherwise, the card remains on the table for future applicants.

8.2.14 Play employee card

Play the employee card and pay its cost. Put three action tokens on a PhD or six on a postdoc. The employees do research for you. PhD students have one action a turn, postdocs have two. They can perform most actions (like doing research, buying devices), but they cannot acquire mentors, flip burgers, see your significant other, trigger events or apply for other positions for you. Once an employee has no more action tokens, they have finished their work for you and are your successful disciples. Having two postdocs as disciples, or one postdoc and two PhDs, gives you the **emeritus victory**.

8.2.15 Play significant other card

There are some people in the world who are not researchers. You can spend time with them to find inspiration. Put the significant other in front of you. Take one ♥. On every future turn, you can now choose to discard one card to the “Left For Further Research” and spend some time with your significant other. This gives you one ♥.

8.2.16 Reviewer #2

Full profs cannot play any language or research cards any more. They can still meet people, purchase books or computers, install programs, flip patties or see their significant others. They can furthermore act as reviewer #2 and discard bad research. This means that they can move the topmost card of the “Left For Further Research” pile to the graveyard pile, up to X times per turn, where X is the number of players in the game. When they uncover an employee, the prof can hire the employee instead of moving the card to the graveyard. Hiring finishes this action for the prof. Employees can still perform further actions, and could also retrieve cards from the “Left For Further Research” pile as described in §8.2 item 2.

8.3 Redraw phase

Draw cards until you reach your hand limit. You cannot draw cards from the “Left For Further Research” pile. It is possible that you will draw more than one card during the redraw phase. It can happen that you have more cards than your current card limit. This is fine. There is no need to discard cards in that case.

9 FAQs

Do language cards give bonuses? No. Language cards have requirements, but they do not give bonuses. All research cards below a language card give you +1 each for the language’s macroarea.

Do macroarea bonuses reduce the cost in ● to explore new languages? No, macroarea bonuses (via books or mentors) reduce the requirements (like PHONOLOGY or MORPHOLOGY). They do not reduce the cost in ●.

When can I hire an employee? In order to hire an employee, you have to be professor. In order to become professor, you have to apply for a position, which in turn requires a publication.

Can I work on several publications at the same time? Yes, you can.

How much time do I have to complete a publication? There is no time limit. You could start a publication on your first turn in the game, even if you have very little chance in finishing a section. The publication then simply sits on your computer waiting for you to find the time and inspiration to continue your work on it. You can spend any number of attempts to write the next section, but each attempt costs you one action and one ♥.

Which actions can I take if I do not have a job? Any action but hiring employees.

Which actions can I take if I am an associate prof? Any action but hiring postdocs.

Which actions can I take if I am full prof? Any action but research cards and language cards.

Which actions can employees take? Research cards, language cards, buy equipment, buy book, install software. Employees cannot play mentors, apply for positions, work on publications, see your significant other, flip patties, play fun cards, play event cards.